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Scalable Data-Rate Near-Lossless Hyperspectral Image Compression Based on Parallel Implementation of CCSDS-123.0-B-2

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CCSDS-123.0-B-2 Overview

- Key elements of new Issue 2:

- Lossless and near-lossless compression => new in-loop **Quantizer** in Predictor
- Sub 1-bit-per-sample compression => new **Hybrid Entropy Coder** option

CCSDS-123.0-B-2 using pre-quantization

- CCSDS 123.0.B-2 In-loop quantizer: data dependencies in BIP order impact throughput performance
- **High-Speed** CCSDS-123.0-B-2 compression can be achieved using an External Quantizer (pre-quantization)
- Proposed CCSDS 123.0-B-2 Hyperspectral Compression Engine (HCE) features:
 - **External Quantization + Lossless Predictor + Hybrid Entropy Coder**
 - Lossless & near-lossless compression
 - User-defined fidelity control per-band
 - High data-rate HW implementation for BIP order => **285 Msamples/s (4.56 Gbps@16bpppb)**

Pre-quantization step

Quantizer implementation:

- Power-of-2 quantization step
- Supports user-defined per-band quantization (fidelity control) for up-to 512 bands
- Hardware friendly implementation

Note: Any HW friendly quantizer can be used (e.g. [1])

[1] D. Valsesia and E. Magli, "High-Throughput Onboard Hyperspectral Image Compression With Ground-Based CNN Reconstruction," IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, vol. 57, no. 12, pp. 9544–9553, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2019.2927434.

CCSDS-123.0-B-2 Predictor (lossless mode)

- CCSDS-123.0-B-2 internal predictor configured in lossless mode

- Predictor architecture as presented in [2][3]
- BIP order
- Full-prediction, neighbor-oriented local sums
- 1 sample-per-cycle operation
- Note: Any CCSDS 123.0-B-2 lossless predictor can be used (e.g. ESA SHyLoC IP)

[2] A. Tsigkanos, N. Kranitis, G. Theodorou, and A. Paschalis, "A 3.3 Gbps CCSDS-123.0-B-1 Multispectral & Hyperspectral Image Compression Hardware Accelerator on a Space-Grade SRAM FPGA," *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 90–103, 2021. DOI: 10.1109/TETC.2018.2854412.

[3] A. Tsigkanos, N. Kranitis, D. Theodoropoulos, and A. Paschalis, "High-Performance COTS FPGA SoC for Parallel Hyperspectral Image Compression With CCSDS-123.0-B-1," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 28, no. 11, pp. 2397–2409, Nov. 2020, ISSN: 1557-9999. DOI: 10.1109/TVLSI.2020.3020164.

CCSDS-123.0-B-2 Hybrid Entropy Coder

Hybrid Entropy Coder as introduced in [4]

- First time in open literature
- 305 Msamples/sec targeting Kintex Ultrascale FPGA
- BIP order
- 1 sample-per-cycle operation
- Potential of sub-1 bit-per-pixel compression

[4] P. Chatziantoniou, A. Tsigkanos, D. Theodoropoulos, N. Kranitis, and A. Paschalis, "An Efficient Architecture and High-Throughput Implementation of CCSDS-123.0-B-2 Hybrid Entropy Coder Targeting Space-Grade SRAM FPGA Technology," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, pp. 1–1, 2022, ISSN: 15579603. DOI: 10.1109/TAES.2022.3173583.

Parallel architecture leveraging segment-level parallelism

- Segmentation provides:
 - Robustness against data corruption
 - High data-rate performance through parallelization
- Image segmentation on **X-axis**
 - Equally good compression performance as Y-axis and better than Z-axis segmentation
 - **Constant embedded memory requirements for spectral slice buffering ($N_x \cdot N_z$)** regardless the number of segments (parallel HCEs)
 - Contrary to Y-axis segmentation HW implementations
- Scalable data-rate performance limited only by device resources and image dimensions

Pre-quantization vs in-loop quantization

- Comparison between CCSDS-123.0-B-2 with in-loop quantization and pre-quantization using *aviris_sc00*
- Measures compression data rate in response to segmentation width (#columns/segment)
- Quantization step selected to keep the same Peak Absolute Error (PAE) on both methods
- Increase in data volume from segmentation may be modest if image segments are not very small

Pre-quantization vs in-loop quantization

- Rate-distortion graph for 1 and 5 parallel cores
- Pre-quantization provides competitive results

Parallel architecture using multiple HCEs

Implementation statistics

- Developed in portable VHDL RTL
- Use of systolic, latency insensitive microarchitecture design pattern
- Statistics provided for Xilinx Kintex-Ultrascale XCKU040-2FFVA1156E FPGA
- Configured for AVIRIS hyperspectral instrument spectral cube dimensions
- Post PnR results from Vivado 2020.2
- Parallel design for up to 5 HCE IP Cores

- **Single Core => 4.56 Gbps**
- **Five Cores => 22.0 Gbps**

Instrument		AVIRIS 680x512x224, 16bpppb				
		1 core	2 cores	3 cores	4 cores	5 cores
Device Resources	LUT	18861 (7.78%)	32033 (13.21%)	44241 (18.25%)	56318 (23.23%)	67362 (27.79%)
	FF	21395 (4.41%)	34597 (7.14%)	47252 (9.75%)	58294 (11.02%)	68987 (14.23%)
	DSP	23 (1.2%)	46 (2.40%)	69 (3.56%)	92 (4.8%)	115 (6%)
	BRAM	104 (17.33%)	276 (46.00%)	295 (49.08%)	296 (49.33%)	306 (51%)
Frequency		285 MHz	280 MHz	275 MHz	270 MHz	275 MHz
Power Est.		1.091 W	3.655 W	3.661 W	3.899 W	4.222 W
MSamples/s		285	560	825	1080	1375
Gbps @16bpppb		4.56	8.96	13.2	17.28	22

Design verification, validation and demonstration

- CCSDS 123.0-B-2 parallel compressor was extensively verified using FPGA-in-the-loop
- Validation & demonstration set-up built around SpaceFibre (ECSS-E-ST-50-11C) interfacing KCU105
 - SpFi + Kintex Ultrascale FPGA technology matching standard space deployment
 - SpFi IP Cores and test equipment (STAR Ultra PCIe) provided by STAR-Dundee
 - In the framework of H2020 Hi-SIDE project (<https://www.hi-side.space/hi-side>)
- Test campaigns (more than 4k tests per campaign)
 - Exhaustive testing of all predictor and hybrid encoder parameters with meaningful quantization steps
- Test automation
 - Test campaigns executed using custom Python scripts that call a custom application based on STAR-System API
 - A single or multiple VCs were used according to the number of HCEs
 - Configuration, control and status of HCEs by accessing RMAP address space
 - Compressed results compared to golden responses based on CNES CCSDS 123.0-B-2 implementation
- Test images: AVIRIS hyperspectral instrument scenes
 - hawaii sc01(614x512x224)
 - maine sc10 (680x512x224)
 - yellowstone sc00 (680x512x224)

Verification, validation and demonstration set-up

- Hardware platform

- Based on a XCKU040 FPGA hosted in Xilinx KCU105 board (supports up to 2 SpFi lanes - demonstrate 2 parallel HCEs)
- Each independently compressed segment is forwarded over a dedicated SpFi VCs (VC1 and VC2)
- STAR Ultra board connected to KCU105 board using QSFP to SFP+ cable assembly

Interfaces

- 128-bit AXI4-Stream I/F per Virtual Channel (VC) (1 VC for data RX, multiple VCs for data TX)
- 32-bit APB I/F: Configuration, Status and Control (through VC0)
- Serdes I/F : Serial Communication with SFP+ cables through GTH transceivers

Configuration, Status and Control

- Use of RMAP registers
- ✓ No need for controller CPU
- ✓ Easier system integration

Demonstration on AIRBUS D&S breadboard

- A CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compressor with 2 parallel HCE IP cores was also validated and demonstrated on an AIRBUS D&S breadboard hosting an XQRKU060 device
 - Compressor element of the High-Speed Data Chain (HSDC) system demo
 - In the framework of H2020 Hi-SIDE project (<https://www.hi-side.space/hi-side>)
- Thus, proposed CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compressor is directly transferable to Xilinx RT Kintex UltraScale XQRKU060 space-grade devices for space deployments

Summary

- Scalable, parallel architecture for CCSDS 123.0-B-2 based compression
 - Leveraging CCSDS 123.0-B-2 segment-level parallelism
 - Single compression engine achieves **285 MSamples/s (4.56 Gbps)**
 - Five parallel compression engines can reach **1.375 GSamples/s (22 Gbps)**
 - Scalability only limited by hyperspectral cube dimensions, available FPGA resources and HSSL technology
- HW friendly prequantization bypasses CCSDS-123.0-B-2 in-loop quantizer data-rate performance bottleneck
- X-axis segmentation: scalable data-rate performance @ **constant BRAM memory footprint**
- FPGA implementation directly transferable to Xilinx RT Kintex UltraScale XQRKU060 space-grade devices
- Validated and demonstrated using state-of-the-art SpaceFibre IP Cores and test equipment to fully match space deployments

Thank you for your attention

Questions?

Part of this research has received funding from the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (HFRI) and the General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT) under the 1st call for H.F.R.I. Research Projects for the support of Post-doctoral Researchers under grant agreement No 990 and part of it has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776151.

Co-financed by the Connecting Europe
Facility of the European Union

Backup Slides

Comparison between segmentation choices

Comparison between segmentation choices

Near-Lossless Compression with CCSDS-123.0-B-2 ($A^*=1$)

Near-Lossless Compression with ext.quantization method ($Q^*=1$)

